

Nitrogen isotope record from a mid-oceanic paleo-atoll limestone to constrain the redox state of the Panthalassa ocean in the Capitanian (Late Guadalupian, Permian)

Masafumi Saitoh^{1,2,3,4}, Manabu Nishizawa^{1,5}, Kazumi Ozaki^{6,7}, Masayuki Ikeda⁸, Yuichiro Ueno^{2,5,7}, Ken Takai⁵, and Yukio Isozaki⁹

¹Laboratory of Ocean-Earth Life Evolution Research (OELE), Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC), Yokosuka, Japan, ²Earth-Life Science Institute, Tokyo Institute of Technology, Tokyo, Japan, ³School of Geosciences and Civil Engineering, Kanazawa University, Kanazawa, Japan, ⁴The University Museum, The University of Tokyo, Tokyo, Japan, ⁵Institute for Extra-cutting-edge Science and Technology Avant-garde Research (X-star), Super-cutting-edge Grand and Advanced Research (SUGAR) Program, Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC), Yokosuka, Japan, ⁶Department of Environmental Science, Toho University, Chiba, Japan, ⁷Department of Earth and Planetary Sciences, Tokyo Institute of Technology, Tokyo, Japan, ⁸Department of Earth and Planetary Environmental Science, The University of Tokyo, Tokyo, Japan, ⁹Department of Earth Science and Astronomy, The University of Tokyo, Tokyo, Japan

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Introduction

In the Supporting Information, we describe the details of blank experiments, the estimation of the potential effect of nitrogen contamination from clay minerals on the bulk $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the analyzed limestone, the compilation of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ changes via HCl rinsing at room temperature in previous studies, the contribution of nitrate in surface waters in the Capitanian ocean on the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the analyzed limestone, the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of seawater nitrate in the intermediate waters and deep-waters of the modern oceans, the estimation of expanded ODZs in the Capitanian ocean, and the stratigraphic relationship between the fossil occurrence and the

$\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the limestone, and the dependency of δ_{PON} in the box U on the upwelling rate of deep-water (R_U) and on the global oceanic redox condition (ΔO_2) in the local upwelling model.

Text S1. Blank experiment.

We describe the details of blank experiments below.

Experiment:

We evaluated the possibility of nitrogen contamination during sample preparation and isotopic analysis, as well as its potential impact on the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values of the samples. For the blank experiments, we used the sea sand (FUJIFILM Wako Pure Chem. Corp., ID: 190-11405, 850~1400 μm in diameter) that had been pre-baked at 450°C for four hours in a muffle furnace.

First, we measured three empty tin cups (LÜDI SWISS AG, art.no.: 176.9807.26; labeled as blank 0-1 to 0-3) to evaluate the nitrogen contamination from tin cups used in the isotope measurements. Next, to evaluate the contamination from the pre-baked sea sand, we measured it wrapped in a tin cup (labeled as blank 1).

Then, we evaluated the nitrogen contamination in the acid treatment. Identical to the acid treatment of the unknown samples, the three baked sea sand samples (labeled as blank 2, 3, and 4) were soaked in 10 M HCl, prepared by diluting the 12 M HCl reagent (Super Special Grade, 35.0-37.0%, FUJIFILM Wako Pure Chem. Corp., ID: 083-03435) with distilled water, at room temperature for overnight (>12 hours). The nitrate concentration of the HCl reagent is not announced officially but its ammonium concentration is <0.2 ppm (<https://labchem-wako.fujifilm.com/jp/product/detail/W01W0108-0343.html>). Similar to the treatment of the unknown sample, the sea sand was then ultrasonically stirred (for 5 min), centrifugated (3000 rpm for 10 min), and diluted with distilled water. These procedures were repeated at least three times. After confirming that the pH had become neutral, the residue was dried overnight in the oven at 70°C and then wrapped in a tin cup.

Finally, we evaluated the nitrogen contamination throughout the pretreatment, including powdering. Similar to the treatment of the unknown samples, ~5 g of the baked sea sand was ultrasonically cleaned with distilled water (10 min, two times) and pure ethanol (10 min, two times). After drying the sand at room temperature, it was powdered using an agate mill. The three powdered sand samples (labeled as blank 5, 6, and 7) were soaked in 10 M HCl at room temperature for overnight. The sand powder was then ultrasonically stirred, centrifugated, and diluted with distilled water, at least three times. After checking the pH, the residue was dried overnight in the oven and wrapped in a tin cup.

Measurement:

Similar to the measurements of the unknown samples, the nitrogen isotopic composition and the nitrogen and carbon amounts in the analyzed tin cups were measured by using a ThermoFinnigan DELTAplus Advantage mass spectrometer coupled with an EA 1112 Series FLASH Elemental Analyzer at JAMSTEC. We measured the blank 1 to 7 three times at different quantities to evaluate heterogeneity in the sample and sample size dependence (labeled as 1-1, 1-2, and 1-3, for example).

Results:

All the results of the blank experiments are shown on Table S3 in Supporting_Data.xlsx. The nitrogen amount in the analyzed tin cups ranged from 0.01 to 0.03 μg , except for one sample (blank 3-3). The nitrogen amount in the blank 3-3 cup was 0.18 μg . No clear correlation

between the sand sample weight and the nitrogen amount was recognized ($r \sim 0.2$). No clear correlation between the carbon and nitrogen amounts was recognized ($r \sim 0.3$). The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of nitrogen in the analyzed tin cups could not be determined as the nitrogen amount was too low for all the measurements.

Discussion:

The raw sea sand (850-1400 μm in diameter) used in the blank experiment is coarse and has a relatively small surface area, so the effect of nitrogen adsorption during acid treatment is considered to be small compared to that of the powdered unknown samples. However, the nitrogen amount did not significantly differ between the non-powdered sand cup (blank 2, 3, and 4) and the powdered sand cup (blank 5, 6, and 7), except for blank 3-3. Moreover, except for the one, the nitrogen amount in the blank 1 to 7 cups was similar to or lower than that in the empty cup (blank 0). This indicates that there was no significant contamination of nitrogen in the pre-treatment procedure, including the powdering and acid treatment.

The nitrogen amount in the blank 3-3 cup was 0.18 μg and substantially high compared to that in other cups. It is a non-powdered sand cup and so it is clear that the nitrogen contamination did not occur in powdering, although the source of contamination is unknown. To estimate the maximum impact of nitrogen contamination during the analytical procedure (from the powdering to isotope analysis) on the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the unknown samples, we assumed that the nitrogen amount in the blank 3-3 cup (0.18 μg) represented the total amount of nitrogen added to each cup of the analyzed unknown samples during the procedure. We then estimated the potential maximum effect of nitrogen contamination during the procedure on the measured $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the unknown samples based on the isotope mass balance. The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of nitrogen in the analyzed blank cups could not be determined due to its low amount, as mentioned above. We therefore assumed that the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the added nitrogen during the procedure was within the typical $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ range of geologic, soil, and plant materials in natural environments (-11‰ to $+24\text{‰}$; Craine et al., 2015).

The amount of nitrogen in the analyzed residue of the Akasaka limestone samples ranges from 5.6 to 45.9 μg (25.1 μg on average). We judged that the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values were measured accurately only for the samples where the amount of nitrogen is higher than 10.8 μg , the minimum amount of nitrogen of the measured running STD L-alanine (Table S1 and S2 in Supporting_Data.xlsx). Assuming that 0.18 μg of nitrogen was added to the analyzed residue, its proportion to the total amount of nitrogen would be less than 2%. Therefore, we estimate that the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ change due to nitrogen contamination was less than 0.4–0.8%, based on the assumption that the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the contaminant was -11‰ and the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the contaminated residue was within the Akasaka $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ range ($+11\text{‰}$ to $+28\text{‰}$). If the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the contaminant was higher than -11‰ , the resultant $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ change would have been smaller.

Based on the results of blank experiments, we concluded that the impact of nitrogen contamination during the analytical procedure (including the powdering, HCl rinsing, and isotope measurements) was negligible in the present study. The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ change due to nitrogen contamination cannot account for the observed large variation in the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the analyzed Akasaka limestone.

Text S2. The effect of potential contamination of clay-bound N on the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the analyzed limestone.

The method and results of estimating the potential maximum contribution of nitrogen from clay minerals to the measured bulk $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the Akasaka limestone are described below (Table S4 in Supporting_Data.xlsx).

For the estimation, we assumed that all components except for organic carbon in the analyzed residue after acid treatment of each sample are clay minerals and/or soil, a potential source of nitrogen (the L column of the "clay_mineral_contribution" sheet in Supporting_Data.xlsx). Based on the residue weight and the TN and TOC contents of the Akasaka limestone, we estimated the content of clay minerals/soil in the residue of each sample. Previous studies have suggested that the ammonium content in clay minerals and/or soil is generally less than 500 ppm (Itihara, 1992; Zhang et al., 2007; Nieder et al., 2011). We assumed that the nitrogen content in clay minerals/soils in the residue was 500 ppm and estimated the proportion of nitrogen from clay minerals/soils in the total nitrogen amount in the analyzed cup (the N column of the "clay_mineral_contribution" sheet).

We assumed that the measured $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the residue was the bulk $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of a mixture of nitrogen from organic matter and from clay minerals. We also assumed that the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of clay mineral-derived nitrogen was -11‰ , the minimum value of the typical $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ range of geologic, soil, and plant materials in natural environments (-11‰ to $+24\text{‰}$; Craine et al., 2015). Then we calculated the estimated $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of nitrogen derived from organic matter in the residue (prior to any contamination of nitrogen from clay minerals) based on the isotope mass balance, and referred to it as ' $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{true}}$ '. We estimated the potential difference between the measured $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value and the $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{true}}$ value (before calibration) (the O column of the "clay_mineral_contribution" sheet).

Our estimation clearly indicates that the potential contamination of nitrogen from clay minerals could have decreased the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the Akasaka limestone. This is due to the fact that the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ range of the Akasaka limestone ($+11\text{‰}$ to $+28\text{‰}$) is relatively high compared to the typical $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ range in natural environments (-11‰ to $+24\text{‰}$). The magnitude of this potential $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ decrease is estimated to be mostly less than 4‰ (1.6‰ on average) at the maximum, except for one sample (06AKA38) where the proportion of nitrogen from clay minerals/soils in the total nitrogen amount in the cup is estimated to be substantially high (34.5%). In fact, the magnitude of the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ decrease due to the contamination of clay-bound nitrogen was likely much smaller than estimated above, as a substantial amount of nitrogen in clay minerals should have been leached during the HCl treatment (Brodie et al., 2011; Schlacher and Connolly, 2014; Fujisaki et al., 2021). We concluded that the potential $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ change due to nitrogen contamination from clay minerals cannot account for the observed large variation in the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the Akasaka limestone.

Text S3. The effect of pre-measurement HCl rinse on the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the analyzed limestone.

The influence of pre-measurement HCl rinse of the analyzed samples on the measured $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value is discussed below.

In the pre-measurement procedure, we removed carbonate in the analyzed limestone by the reaction with HCl ('rinse method'; Brodie et al., 2011), due to the low TN and TOC contents of the analyzed rocks (Table 2). Previous studies reported that the bulk $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of sediments can be altered by HCl rinse, due to losses of nitrogen in clay minerals and/or acid soluble organic matter (Brodie et al., 2011; Schlacher and Connolly, 2014; Fujisaki et al., 2021). A compilation of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ changes via HCl rinse at room temperature (similar to in the present study)

in previous studies shows that the magnitude of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ changes (the difference between the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value after HCl rinse ($\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{acidified}}$) and the value before HCl rinse ($\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{untreated}}$); $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{acidified}} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{untreated}}$) mostly ranges from -2‰ to $+1\text{‰}$ (Table S5 in Supporting_Data.xlsx). (A study in which excess HCl was removed by heating (at 60°C , for example) after rinsing was excluded from the compilation.) We regarded this magnitude of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ changes (-2‰ to $+1\text{‰}$) reported in previous studies as the potential $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ changes of our samples via HCl rinse.

Based on these potential $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ changes of our samples (-2‰ to $+1\text{‰}$), we considered the potential uncertainty of the possible maximum ΔO_2 and minimum δ_{D} in the Capitanian ocean, estimated from the present Akasaka $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ record and the local upwelling model (Figure 8). As mentioned in Sec. 4.2.1 in the main text, we estimated that the possible maximum ΔO_2 and minimum δ_{D} in the Capitanian ocean were $-80\ \mu\text{M}$ and $+9\text{‰}$, respectively (the right figure in Figure 8b). Previous studies illustrated that the trend and magnitude of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ changes via HCl rinse are similar in sediments with the same lithology from the same location (e.g., Wang et al., 2018 ; Nishizawa et al., 2019). We therefore assumed that the magnitude of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ changes of the analyzed samples via HCl rinse was consistent through the Akasaka limestone succession. Under this assumption, the supposed $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ changes of the analyzed samples would shift the red line/parallelogram up or down in each figure of Figure 8b. This is based on the maximum and minimum δ_{PON} contours shown in Figure 8a. For example, when the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of each of our samples decreased consistently by 1‰ via HCl rinse, the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values of the Akasaka limestone before HCl rinse should have ranged from $+12\text{‰}$ to $+29\text{‰}$. In this case, the position of the line/parallelogram representing the possible range of ΔO_2 and δ_{D} , on which the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ range before HCl rinse ($+12\text{‰}$ to $+29\text{‰}$) is fully covered, would be 1‰ higher than the present position shown in each figure of Figure 8b.

Hence, while the potential $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ changes of the analyzed samples via HCl rinse would directly affect the estimate of δ_{D} , it would not affect the estimate of ΔO_2 in the present modeling. Under these circumstances, we regarded the potential $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ changes via HCl rinse (-2‰ to $+1\text{‰}$) as the potential uncertainty of the estimated δ_{D} in the Capitanian ocean, and concluded that the possible maximum ΔO_2 and minimum δ_{D} in the Capitanian ocean were $-80\ \mu\text{M}$ and $+9\text{‰}$ $\pm 1\text{‰}$, respectively.

Text S4. The variation in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of the Akasaka limestone records that of nitrate in Panthalassic surface waters?

The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of seawater nitrate in the modern shallow oceans (water depths $< 200\ \text{m}$) shows a large variation of up to 38‰ (Fripiat et al., 2021). Thus, one may ask if the large variation in the Akasaka $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{acid.}}$ record ($+11\text{‰}$ to $+28\text{‰}$) originated from the variation in the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of nitrate in surface waters in the Capitanian ocean. However, observations of the modern oceans reject this possibility as shown below.

In the modern oceans, the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of nitrate in surface waters (water depths $< 200\ \text{m}$) ranges from -0.4‰ to $+37.5\text{‰}$ on a global scale ($+8.8\text{‰}$ on average; $n=4292$) (Fripiat et al., 2021), which was largely caused by the nitrogen isotope fractionation via partial nitrate assimilation during lateral advection of surface water. In marked contrast, the bulk $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of surface sediment in the shallow oceans (water depths $< 200\ \text{m}$) is less variable and ranges from $+2.5\text{‰}$ to $+15.0\text{‰}$ on a global scale ($+7.1\text{‰}$ on average; $n=617$) (Tesdal et al., 2013). Hence, it is clear that the observed large variation in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of seawater nitrate in the surface waters is not recorded simply in the bulk $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ records of shallow-marine sediments. In particular, the nitrate concentration of surface water in which the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of nitrate is high ($> +15\text{‰}$) is generally very low ($< 0.6\ \mu\text{M}$) in the modern open ocean, and its substantially high $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value is not recorded in the bulk $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of surface sediments. This is because

subsurface nitrate supplied through (seasonally-driven) vertical mixing of water mass is the main nitrogen source for primary production (e.g., Waniek, 2003).

These modern observations strongly suggest that, in the Capitanian ocean, it is difficult to interpret the high $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values of the Akasaka limestone (+11‰ to +28‰) straightforwardly as the high $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values of nitrate in surface waters (+11‰ to +28‰) around the seamount top in mid-Panthalassa. In other words, other mechanisms to supply fixed nitrogen into the surface waters, i.e., nitrogen fixation in the surface water and/or upwelling of nutrient-bearing subsurface water whose nitrate was essentially derived from the intermediate and deep-water masses, are required to explain the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ record of the Akasaka limestone. That clearly supports the validity of our local upwelling model in which these mechanisms for fixed nitrogen supply were carefully examined.

In general, in the modern oceans, marine nitrogen cycling processes and the oceanic redox conditions on a global scale are recorded in the nitrogen isotopic composition of a deep-oceanic nitrate reservoir. And then, on a regional scale, the nitrogen isotopic composition of the global deep-oceanic nitrate reservoir is approximately reflected to that of the intermediate water nitrate (Sigman and Fripiat, 2019; Fripiat et al., 2021). Hence, some information about the global nitrogen cycle and redox conditions in the Capitanian ocean could have been indirectly recorded in the Akasaka limestone, as discussed in detail in the main text (Section 5).

Text S5. The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of seawater nitrate in the intermediate and deep waters of the modern oceans.

In Text S4 above, the variation in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of seawater nitrate in the modern shallow oceans (water depths < 200 m) was summarized. As a separate matter from that, the observed variation in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of seawater nitrate in the intermediate waters (200 m < water depths < 1000 m) and in the deep part (water depths > 1000 m) of the modern oceans is summarized below. We incorporated this observational fact into the local upwelling model in the present study.

In the modern oceans, a vertical gradient in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of seawater nitrate in the water column on a regional scale is commonly observed, although the difference in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of nitrate between the intermediate waters (200 m < water depths < 1000 m; corresponding to the box I in the present upwelling model; Figure 2) and the deep part of the ocean (water depths > 1000 m; corresponding to the box D) is at most ~2‰. For example, in the equatorial Pacific, the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of nitrate in the intermediate water is ca. +7‰ whereas the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value in the deep part of the ocean is +5~6‰ (Rafter et al. (2012). In contrast, in the subtropical North Atlantic, the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of nitrate in the intermediate water is relatively low (ca. +3‰) compared to the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value in the deep part of the ocean (ca. +5‰) (Bourbonnais et al., 2009; Marconi et al., 2015). This relatively low $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of nitrate in intermediate water in the subtropical North Atlantic is attributed to nitrogen fixation in surface water and vertical mixing between the surface and subsurface waters. Nevertheless, a compilation of nitrate record through the whole Atlantic Ocean shows that there is no significant difference between the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of nitrate in the intermediate water (+4.7‰ on average; n=1376) and in the deep part of the ocean (+4.9‰ on average; n=1273) (Fripiat et al., 2021). Collectively, the difference in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of nitrate between the intermediate waters and the deep-waters is at most 2‰ in the modern oceans.

In the local upwelling model in the present study, we consider both of the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of nitrate in the intermediate box I (δ_I) and the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value in the deep part of the ocean (box D) (δ_D), as shown in Table A1 in the main text. As the volume of the box D is assumed to be >95%

of global ocean volume, δ_D can be regarded as $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{NO}_3}$, the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of a deep-oceanic nitrate reservoir in the global nitrogen isotope mass balance (Figure 3a in the main text). Based on the modern observations, in the present model, we considered the potential difference in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value between the intermediate waters and the deep part of the Capitanian ocean. We assumed that, in the Capitanian ocean, the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of nitrate in the intermediate waters and in the deep part of the ocean differ to the same degree as in the modern oceans. The difference in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ between the intermediate waters and the deep part of the modern ocean is at most $\sim 2\text{‰}$, as mentioned above. We therefore assumed that δ_I ranges from $\delta_D - 2\text{‰}$ to $\delta_D + 2\text{‰}$. Under this constraint condition, we calculated the modeling and constrained the possible minimum value of δ_D (i.e., $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{NO}_3}$) in the Capitanian ocean, as discussed in the main text.

Text S6. The estimation of expanded ODZs in the Capitanian ocean.

The estimation of expanded ODZs in the Capitanian ocean based on the possible minimum $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{NO}_3}$ in the global nitrogen isotope mass balance (i.e., δ_D in the local upwelling model) is described below (Table S9 in “Supporting_Data.xlsx”).

Based on the Akasaka $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{acid}}$ record, we estimated that the possible minimum δ_D , the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of seawater nitrate in the deep ocean, in the local upwelling model was $+9 +2/-1\text{‰}$ in the Capitanian (Figure 8b). δ_D in the local upwelling model (Figure 2) corresponds to $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{NO}_3}$, the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value of an oceanic nitrate reservoir, in the global isotope mass balance (Figure 3) in the present modeling. Accordingly, we estimate the possible minimum volume of the ODZs on a global scale in the Capitanian ocean with three simple assumptions as follows. First, the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value and size of oceanic nitrate reservoir were constant during the stage. (It is the assumption of the nitrogen isotope mass balance in the ocean.) Second, the volumetric rate of water-column denitrification in the Capitanian ODZ was identical to that in the modern ODZ. Finally, a global flux of sedimentary denitrification in the Capitanian ocean was consistently fixed to that in the modern oceans.

Under those assumptions, we supposed that the volume of ODZs in the Capitanian ocean was K -fold larger relative to that in the modern oceans (Table S9 in “Supporting_Data.xlsx”). In this case, the global flux of water-column denitrification was K -fold higher relative to in the modern oceans (based on the second assumption above) and the f value can be described as follows:

$$f = \frac{0.27K}{0.73 + 0.27K} \quad (1)$$

As f and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{NO}_3}$ have a linear relationship in the global isotope mass balance (Figure 3b in the main text), at the given $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{NO}_3}$ value of $+9\text{‰}$, the expanded ODZs were estimated to occupy at least $\sim 0.5\%$ of the global ocean volume in the Capitanian. When the uncertainty of estimated δ_D (according to the potential $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ changes of the analyzed rocks via HCl rinsing) is considered ($\delta_D = \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{NO}_3} = +9 +2/-1\text{‰}$), the ODZs constituted $\sim 0.5 +0.3/-0.1\%$ of global ocean volume at the minimum in the ocean. Hence, we concluded that the volume of ODZs in the Capitanian ocean was at least twice as much as in the modern ocean.

Figure S1. Fossil group ranges and the $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{acid}}$ stratigraphy of the analyzed Akasaka limestone. E.H.: extinction horizon.

Figure S2. Calculated results of the local upwelling model. Plot shows the dependency of δ_{PON} in the box U on the upwelling rate of deep-water (R_U) and ΔO_2 with δ_i and δ_D of +4.9‰. The default values in Table A1 were used for the calculations.

Table S1. Analytical results of STD measurements.

Table S2. Analytical results of the Akasaka limestone.

Table S3. Results of blank experiments.

Table S4. Isotope effect of potential N contamination from clay minerals.

Table S5. Previous results of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ changes via HCl rinsing at room temperature.

Table S6. Upwelling model results at the standard oceanic condition.

Table S7. Upwelling model results in the non-N-fixation case.

Table S8. Upwelling model results in the N-fixation case.

Table S9. The estimated minimum volume of expanded ODZs in the Capitanian ocean.

References from the Supporting Information.

Bourbonnais, A., Lehmann, M.F., Waniek, J.J., & Schulz-Bull, D.E. (2009). Nitrate isotope anomalies reflect N₂ fixation in the Azores Front region (subtropical NE Atlantic). *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 114, C03003, DOI: 10.1029/2007JC004617

- Brodie, C.R., Heaton, T.H.E., Leng, M.J., Kendrick, C.P., Casford, J.S.L., & Lloyd, J.M. (2011). Evidence for bias in measured $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values of terrestrial and aquatic organic materials due to pre-analysis acid treatment methods. *Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry*, 25, 1089–1099. DOI: 10.1002/rcm.4970
- Bunn, S.E., Loneragan, N.R., & Kempster, M.A. (1995). Effects of acid washing on stable isotope ratios of C and N in penaeid shrimp and seagrass: implications for food-web studies using multiple stable isotopes. *Limnology and Oceanography*, 40, 622–625.
- Carabel, S., Godinez-Dominguez, E., Verisimo, P., Fernandez, L., & Freire, J. (2006). An assessment of sample processing methods for stable isotope analyses of marine food webs. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 336, 254–261. DOI: 10.1016/j.jembe.2006.06.001
- Craine, J.M., Brookshire, E.N.J., Cramer, M.D., Hasselquist, N.J., Koba, K., Marin-Spiotta, E., & Wang, L. (2015). Ecological interpretations of nitrogen isotope ratios of terrestrial plants and soils. *Plant and Soil*, 396, 1–26. DOI: 10.1007/s11104-015-2542-1
- Fripiat, F., Marconi, D., Rafter, P.A., Sigman, D.M., Altabet, M.A., Bourbonnais, A., Brandes, J., Casciotti, K.L., Deman, F., Dehairs, F., Emeis, K.-C., Fawcett, S., Galbraith, E.D., Gaye, B., Granger, J., Harms, N., Haug, G.H., Kemeny, P.C., Kienast, M., Knapp, A.N., Kopf, S., Lehmann, M.F., Luu, V.H., Martin, T., Martínez-García, A., Pantoja, S., Peng, X., Peters, B., Smart, S., Trull, T.W., Van Oostende, N., Voss, M., Yoshikawa, C., Zhang, R., & Dähnke, K. (2021). Compilation of nitrate $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ in the ocean. PANGAEA. DOI: 10.1594/PANGAEA.936484
- Fujisaki, W., Matsui, Y., Ueda, H., Sawaki, Y., Suzuki, K., & Maruoka, T. (2021). Pre-treatment Methods for Accurate Determination of Total Nitrogen and Organic Carbon Contents and their Stable Isotopic Compositions: Re-evaluation from Geological Reference Materials. *Geostandards and Geoanalytical Research*, 46, 5–19. DOI: 10.1111/ggr.12410
- Itihara, Y. (1992). Recent studies on ammonium in rocks. *Journal of Geological Society of Japan*, 98, 885–899 (in Japanese with English abstract).
- Kolasinski, J., Rogers, K., & Patrick Frouin, P. (2008). Effects of acidification on carbon and nitrogen stable isotopes of benthic macrofauna from a tropical coral reef. *Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry*, 22, 2955–2960. DOI: 10.1002/rcm.3694
- Lorrain, A., Savoye, N., Chauvaud, L., Paulet, Y.M., & Naulet, N. (2003). Decarbonation and preservation method for the analysis of organic C and N contents and stable isotope ratios of low-carbonated suspended particulate material. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 491, 125–133. DOI:10.1016/S0003-2670(03)00815-8
- Marconi, D., Weigand, M.A., Rafter, P.A., McIlvin, M.R., Forbes, M., Casciotti, K.L., & Sigman, D.M. (2015). Nitrate isotope distributions on the US GEOTRACES North Atlantic cross-basin section: Signals of polar nitrate sources and low latitude nitrogen cycling. *Marine Chemistry*, 177, 143–156. DOI: 10.1016/j.marchem.2015.06.007
- Nieder, R., Benbi, D.K., & Scherer, H.W. (2011). Fixation and defixation of ammonium in soils: a review. *Biol Fertil Soils*, 47, 1–14. DOI: 10.1007/s00374-010-0506-4
- Nishizawa, M., Tsuchiya, Y., Du, W., Sawaki, Y., Matsui, Y., Wang, Y., Han, J., & Komiya, T. (2019). Shift in limiting nutrients in the late Ediacaran–early Cambrian marine systems of South China. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 530, 281–299. DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.05.036
- Peters B.D., Lam, P.J., & Casciotti, K.L. (2018). Nitrogen and oxygen isotope measurements of nitrate along the US GEOTRACES Eastern Pacific Zonal Transect (GP16) yield insights into nitrate supply, remineralization, and water mass transport. *Marine Chemistry*, 201, 137–150. DOI: 10.1016/j.marchem.2017.09.009

- Rafter P. A., Sigman D. M., Charles C. D., Kaiser J. and Haug G. H. (2012) Subsurface tropical Pacific nitrogen isotopic composition of nitrate: Biogeochemical signals and their transport. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles*, 26, GB1003. DOI: 10.1029/2010GB003979
- Schlacher, T.A., & Connolly, R.M. (2014). Effects of acid treatment on carbon and nitrogen stable isotope ratios in ecological samples: a review and synthesis. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 5, 541–550. DOI: 10.1111/2041-210X.12183
- Syvaranta, J., Vesala, S., Rask, M., Ruuhijarvi, J., & Jones, R.I. (2008). Evaluating the utility of stable isotope analyses of archived freshwater sample materials. *Hydrobiologia*, 600, 121–130. DOI: 10.1007/s10750-007-9181-3
- Tesdal, J.-E., Galbraith, E.D., & Kienast, M. (2013). Nitrogen isotopes in bulk marine sediment: linking seafloor observations with subseafloor records. *Biogeosciences*, 10, 101–118. DOI: 10.5194/bg-10-101-2013
- Ventura, M., & Jeppesen, E. (2010). Evaluating the need for acid treatment prior to $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ analysis of freshwater fish scales: effects of varying scale mineral content, lake productivity and CO_2 concentration. *Hydrobiologia*, 644, 245–259. DOI: 10.1007/s10750-010-0121-2
- Wang, X.Q., Jiang, G.Q., Shi, X.Y., Peng, Y.B., & Morales, D.C. (2018). Nitrogen isotope constraints on the early Ediacaran ocean redox structure. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 240, 220–235. DOI: 10.1016/j.gca.2018.08.034
- Waniek, J.J. (2003). The role of physical forcing in initiation of spring blooms in the northeast Atlantic. *Journal of Marine Systems*, 39, 57– 82. DOI:10.1016/S0924-7963(02)00248-8
- Yokoyama, H., Tamaki, A., Harada, K., Shimoda, K., Koyama, K., & Ishihi, Y. (2005). Variability of diet-tissue isotopic fractionation in estuarine macrobenthos. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 296, 115–128. DOI:10.3354/meps296115
- Yokoyama, H., & Ishihi, Y. (2006). Variation in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ among different tissues of three estuarine bivalves: implications for dietary reconstructions. *Plankton and Benthos Research*, 1, 178–182. DOI: 10.3800/pbr.1.178
- Zhang, Y.Z., Huang, S.H., Wan, D.J., Huang, Y.X., Zhou, W.J., & Zou, Y.B. (2007). Fixed Ammonium Content and Maximum Capacity of Ammonium Fixation in Major Types of Tillage Soils in Hunan Province, China. *Agricultural Sciences in China*, 6, 466–474.